

EXPLORING THE RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN THE KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS OF AIRLINES

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2024

ABSTRACT

In this paper, we apply the formal approach to explore the relationships between the key performance indicators of airlines. We concentrate on the passenger transportation in this paper however this formal approach can be applied to the mixed (passenger and cargo) or to the full cargo transportation as well.

Key words:

Profit, yield, unit cost, Load Factor, seat occupancy, network effect, key performance indicators.

1. Modification of the basic airline Profit equation

To modify the widely referred basic airline Profit equation let's introduce the following symbols:

P_a	Capacity–Available Seat Kilometres (ASK)
P_r	Traffic– Revenue Passenger Kilometres (RPK)
R	Operating (Passenger) revenue
C	Operating cost
E	Economic result (Operating Profit or Loss)
λ	Passenger Load Factor (%)
y	Yield – total passenger revenue per RPK
c	Unit cost – total operating cost per ASK (CASK)

The basic airline Profit equation as it is widely referred in relevant literature:

$$\text{Operating Profit} = (\text{Revenue}) - (\text{Operating Costs}) = \text{RPK} \times \text{Yield} - \text{ASK} \times \text{Unit Cost}$$

This equation is intended to focus on Profit however it provides an incomplete understanding of the relationship between the Profit drivers such as yield, unit cost and Load Factor.

Steps:

1. Economic result (operating Profit or Loss):

$$E = R - C \tag{1}$$

2. Yield:

$$y = \frac{R}{P_r} \rightarrow R = yP_r \tag{2}$$

3. Unit cost (CASK):

$$c = \frac{C}{P_a} \rightarrow C = cP_a \tag{3}$$

4. Economic result again:

$$E = y P_r - c P_a \tag{4}$$

5. Introducing the Load Factor:

$$\lambda = \frac{P_r}{P_a} \rightarrow P_r = \lambda P_a \tag{5}$$

6. Economic result once again:

$$E = y \lambda P_a - c P_a \tag{6}$$

7. Finally:

$E = P_a(\lambda y - c)$	(7)
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From the widely referred basic airline Profit equation we arrived to the modified model which allows us to analyse the relationship between the economic result (Profit/Loss) and the basic variables (Profit drivers).

The model (7) links financials (Profit – revenue – cost) and operational metrics (capacity – traffic – Passenger Load Factor).

As it seen from the model (7) the economic result (consequently the Profitability) of an airline depends on the interplay of three basic variables such as: unit cost, yield and Load Factor.

There is an inverse relationship between the yield and Load Factor. To reach the same Profit when yield is decreasing, we have to increase Load Factor and vice versus (Figure 1).

Let us assume that we have a version of an economic plan based on the given airline schedule and as a consequence the capacity and the unit cost — disregarding the passenger related costs — are constant, we can build an **isoprofit curve** - applying equation (7) - along which the any combination of the yield and the Load Factor results the same Profit.

FIGURE 1

Any combination of the yield and the Load Factor along the curve results in the same Profit

Remark: Operating costs contains some passenger related costs (e.g., catering costs). In other words, part of the unit cost depends on the seat occupancy which is connected to the Load Factor through network effect coefficient (see later in chapter 3.).

2. Break-even Load Factor (%)

In case of break-even: $E=0$.

From equation (7) the break-even Load Factor (λ_b):

$$\lambda_b = \frac{c}{y} \quad (8)$$

Break-even Load Factor is the quotient of the unit cost and the yield.

3. Seat-occupancy and the network effect

3.1. Seat-occupancy or Seat Load Factor (%)

Seat-occupancy (λ_s) is the quotient of the number of revenue passengers carried (N_r) and the number of seats dispatched (N_s). In other words: Seat Load Factor represents the **total number of seats sold** as a percentage of **total seat capacity** on all sectors flown.

$$\lambda_s = \frac{N_r}{N_s} \quad (9)$$

3.2. Network effect

The Passenger Load Factor and the seat-occupancy on a single stage are equal to each other, but on the network, they are usually different from each other. The stage refers to a single flight between two airports.

The average trip length is varying depending on the demand for shorter or longer travel distances. This variation leads us to the network effect.

To arrive to the network effect formal expression let's introduce the following symbols:

- l_h Average seat-haul (km)
- l_t Average trip length or passenger haul (km)
- d_n Network effect coefficient

Average seat-haul is the distance of hauling one aircraft seat — empty and occupied by a passenger — on the network during the planning period.

The **average seat-haul** (km) is the quotient of the capacity and the total number of seats dispatched:

$$l_h = \frac{P_a}{N_s} \quad (10)$$

From equation (10) the capacity.

$$P_a = l_h N_s \quad (11)$$

Dividing the total number of revenue kilometres (traffic) by the total number of revenue passengers carried during the planning period we get the **average trip length** or average passenger haul (km):

$$l_t = \frac{P_r}{N_r} \quad (12)$$

The traffic from (12):

$$P_r = N_r l_t \quad (13)$$

The Passenger Load Factor applying equations (13) and (11):

$$\lambda = \frac{P_r}{P_a} = \frac{l_t N_r}{l_h N_s} \quad (14)$$

The quotient of the average trip length and the seat haul we will refer as network effect coefficient.

$$d_n = \frac{l_t}{l_h} \quad (15)$$

In case if $d_n > 1$ the demand for travel distances longer than the average seat haul is prevailing over the demand for travel distances shorter than the average seat haul, and inversely if $d_n < 1$.

Substituting (9) and (15) into (14) the passenger Load Factor:

$$\lambda = \lambda_s d_n \quad (16)$$

In a specific case when the average trip length equals average seat-haul ($d_n=1$) the Load Factor equals seat occupancy.

The shift of passengers to the higher travel distances has a significant impact on the Profit of the airline.

4. Break-even seat occupancy (%)

Having the network effect coefficient, we can formulate the equation for break-even seat occupancy (λ_{bs}).

Applying equation (16) the revised Profit model (7) looks like:

$$E = P_a (\lambda_s d_n y - c) \quad (17)$$

In case of break-even the Profit equals zero: $E=0$

From equation (17) we can arrive to the break-even seat occupancy:

$$\lambda_{bs} = \frac{c}{d_n y} \quad (18)$$

The break-even seat occupancy or break-even Seat-Factor equals break-even Load Factor if $d_n=1$ (passenger-haul equals seat-haul). With the help of the break-even seat factor, we can calculate the number of passengers at the break-even point.

5. Average fare and the yield

Let's introduce symbol (f_p) for the average passenger fare.

$$f_p = \frac{R}{N_r} \rightarrow R = N_r f_p \quad (19)$$

Applying equations (19) and (13) we get the **second** equation for the yield:

$$y = \frac{R}{P_r} = \frac{N_r f_p}{N_r l_t} = \frac{f_p}{l_t} \quad (20)$$

The yield can be calculated by dividing the average passenger fare by the average trip length as well.

6. Average cost per seat and the unit cost

Let's introduce the symbols (c_s) for the average cost per seat and (l_s) for the average stage length.

$$c_s = \frac{C}{N_s} \rightarrow C = c_s N_s \quad (21)$$

Applying equations (21) and (11) we get the **second** equation for the unit cost:

$$c = \frac{C}{P_a} = \frac{c_s N_s}{l_h N_s} = \frac{c_s}{l_h} = \frac{c_s}{l_s} \quad (22)$$

The unit cost can be calculated by dividing the average cost per seat by the average seat haul or by the average stage length. For a given network structure and schedule, the average seat haul equals average stage length. The proof you find in the **Appendix 1**.

7. Profit model based on unit revenue (RASK) and unit cost (CASK)

Let's introduce the symbol (r) for the unit revenue. We get the unit revenue dividing the revenue (R) by the capacity (P_a).

$$r = \frac{R}{P_a} \rightarrow R = rP_a \quad (23)$$

From equation (2):

$$R = yP_r \quad (24)$$

Comparing equations (23) and (24):

$$rP_a = yP_r \rightarrow r = y \frac{P_r}{P_a} \quad (25)$$

Applying equation (5) from (25) we get:

$$r = \lambda y \text{ (RASK)} \quad (26)$$

Profit equation (7) can be formulated:

$E = P_a(r - c)$	(27)
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We can get the Profit/Loss by multiplying the capacity with the difference between the unit revenue and the unit cost (RASK-CASK).

8. Profit model based on average revenue per seat and average cost per seat

Average revenue per seat:

$$r_s = \frac{R}{N_s} \rightarrow R = r_s N_s \quad (28)$$

Applying equations (1), (28) and (21) the economic result:

$$E = R - C = r_s N_s - c_s N_s \quad (29)$$

$E = N_s(r_s - c_s)$	(30)
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We can get the Profit/Loss by multiplying the number of seats dispatched with the difference between the average revenue per seat and the average cost per seat.

9. Profit model based on cost per RPK (CRPK) and yield

Costs could also be measured by RPK, but measuring costs by ASK is more relevant and therefore very common. To set up a profit model based on cost per RPK let's introduce the symbol (c_r) for Cost per Revenue Passenger Kilometres (CRPK).

$$c_r = \frac{C}{P_r} \quad (31)$$

From the equation (5) of the Load Factor:

$$P_r = \lambda P_a \quad (32)$$

Applying (32) from (31) we get:

$$c_r = \frac{C}{\lambda P_a} \quad (33)$$

Modifying (33) we arrive to unit cost:

$$c_r \lambda = \frac{C}{P_a} = c \quad (34)$$

Substituting (34) into (7)

$$E = P_a(\lambda y - c_r \lambda) \quad (35)$$

Modifying equation (35):

$$E = \lambda P_a(y - c_r) \quad (36)$$

Taking (32) into account we get:

$E = P_r(y - c_r)$	(37)
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We can get the Profit/Loss by multiplying the traffic with the difference between the yield and the cost per Revenue Passenger Kilometres.

Remark: The result of equations (7), (27), (30) and (37) can be different from the result of equation (1) when you calculate the economic result. This difference depends on the applied number of decimals.

10. Profitability (¢/ASK)

Available seat kilometre (ASK) is the fundamental unit of production for a passenger-carrying airline and in other words it is the unit of quantity produced.

Profitability (e) shows how much Profit is generated with one unit of production. The Profitability is the quotient of the result (E) and the capacity (P_a).

$$e = \frac{E}{P_a} \quad (38)$$

Based on equation (27) Profitability is the difference between the unit revenue (RASK) and the unit cost (CASK) and so:

$$e = \frac{E}{P_a} = r - c \quad (39)$$

The Profitability is expressed in US cent per available seat kilometre on Figure 2.

Profitability is the difference between unit revenue (RASK) and unit cost (CASK)

11. Operating Profit Margin (%)

The operating Profit margin ratio (O_{pm}) compares the operating Profit of an airline to the total operating revenue generated.

$$O_{pm} = \frac{E}{R} \quad (40)$$

Taking into account equations (27) and (23) the Operating Profit Margin:

$$O_{pm} = \frac{P_a(r-c)}{rP_a} = \frac{r-c}{r} = \frac{e}{r} \quad (41)$$

Operating Profit Margin can be expressed as a quotient of the Profitability and the unit revenue (RASK).

12. Closing notes

We applied the formal approach to explore the relationships between the airline's performance indicators. The Profit model $E = P_a(\lambda y - c)$ could be a tool to adjust the unit cost, the yield and the Load Factor to produce their optimal combinations during the planning process.

We found further models for the economic result. We introduced further models for the yield, unit cost, Load Factor and Profit margin. These models could be applied for the verification of the correlation between the data of the airline's annual reports. We introduced the concept of the network effect. While our focus in this paper is on passenger transportation, this formal approach is applicable to mixed (passenger and cargo) or solely cargo transportation too. For the models to be applicable, we must ensure a clear distinction between passenger transportation data and cargo transportation data, especially concerning their associated costs.

The summary of airline's performance indicator's equations is in **Appendix 2.** and the list of symbols in **Appendix 3.**

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APPENDIXES

Appendix 1. Average seat-haul equals average stage length (the proof)

Let's introduce the symbols:

l_f Total distance flown per aircraft departures (km)

N_d Number of departures

Average stage length (km) is the average distance flown per aircraft departure:

$$l_s = \frac{l_f}{N_d} \quad (42)$$

We can get the capacity by multiplying the average stage length by the number of seats available for sale:

$$P_a = l_s N_s \quad (43)$$

The capacity as in equation (11):

$$P_a = l_h N_s$$

Comparing equations (11) and (43) we find:

$$l_s N_s = l_h N_s \quad (44)$$

After reduction with the number of seats:

$$l_h = l_s \quad (45)$$

Appendix 2. Summary of equations

Economic result (Profit or Loss)	Number of the equation
$E = R - C$	(1)
$E = P_a(\lambda y - c)$	(7)
$E = P_a(r - c)$	(27)
$E = N_s(r_s - c_s)$	(30)
$E = P_r(y - c_r)$	(37)
Passenger Load Factor	

$\lambda = \frac{P_r}{P_a}$	(5)
$\lambda = \lambda_s d_n$	(16)
Yield	
$y = \frac{R}{P_r}$	(2)
$y = \frac{f_p}{l_t}$	(20)
Unit cost	
$c = \frac{C}{P_a}$	(3)
$c = \frac{c_s}{l_s}$	(22)
Profitability (¢/ASK)	
$e = \frac{E}{P_a}$	(38)
$e = r - c$	(39)
Operating Profit Margin (%)	
$O_{pm} = \frac{E}{R}$	(40)
$O_{pm} = \frac{e}{r}$	(41)

Appendix 3. List of symbols

No	Designation	Measure	Symbols
1.	Average cost per seat	(USD/seat)	c_s
2.	Average passenger fare	(USD/PAX)	f_p
3.	Average seat-haul	(km)	l_h
4.	Average stage length	(km)	l_s
5.	Average trip length or passenger-haul	(km)	l_t
6.	Break-even Load Factor	(%)	λ_b
7.	Break-even seat occupancy	(%)	λ_{bs}

8.	Capacity	(ASK) Available Seat Kilometres	P_a
9.	Cost per Revenue Passenger Kilometres	CRPK	c_r
10.	Economic result (Profit or Loss)	(USD)	E
11.	Kilometres flown	(km)	l_f
12.	Network effect coefficient		d_n
13.	Number of departures		N_d
14.	Number of revenue passengers	(PAX)	N_r
15.	Number of seats dispatched	(Seats)	N_s
16.	Operating costs	(USD)	C
17.	Operating Profit margin	(%)	O_{pm}
18.	Passenger Load Factor	(%)	λ
19.	Passenger revenue	(USD)	R
20.	Profitability	(¢/ASK)	e
21.	Revenue per seat	(USD/seat)	r_s
22.	Seat occupancy	(%)	λ_s
23.	Traffic	(RPK) Revenue Passenger Kilometres	P_r
24.	Unit cost CASK	(¢/ASK)	c
25.	Unit revenue RASK	(¢/ASK)	r
26.	Yield	(¢/RPK)	y